

Seasonal variation in kernel and hull weight of IR29723-143-3-2-1 in the monthly planting experiment. IRRI, 1989.

In IR29723-143-3-2-1, hull and kernel weight varied remarkably with transplanting date (see figure). The trend with IR58 was similar. Hull weights of grain harvested from Sep to Nov were higher than those of grain harvested in other months. Kernel weight variations were similar to those of hull weight. Thus, the hull weight ratio (HWR—hull weight divided by grain weight) was almost constant through the year. This means that HWR could be a useful, stable indicator in screening for cultivars with lower hull weight.

Varietal difference in hull weight ratio (hull weight/grain weight). IRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Hull weight ratio ^a
Binato	0.26 ± 0.005
Peta	0.28 ± 0.002
IR8	0.29 ± 0.002
IR32	0.28 ± 0.002
IR58	0.30 ± 0.002
IR64	0.27 ± 0.008
IR65	0.28 ± 0.007
IR54752B	0.32 ± 0.004
IR25588-7-3-1	0.25 ± 0.001
IR29723-143-3-2-1	0.23 ± 0.002

^aA_v = 0.28.

Clear differences in HWR were found in the 10 cultivars compared (see table). (The lowest HWR found was still much higher than the ratio of wheat chaff weight to total grain weight.)

Seasonal and varietal differences in hull weights suggest the possibility of breeding rice with a lower HWR. It would be worthwhile to examine the extent of HWR variation in rice and to determine its heritability. ■

Computer simulation of the potential production of rice

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The MACROS model simulates physiological and physical processes by which meteorological variables affect the growth and development of rice. Crop parameters, weather variables, and management factors are inputs in the model. Values of state variables, such as the weights of different plant organs, and of rate variables, such as photosynthetic rate, are computed progressively for each day of the growing season.

We used MACROS to calculate potential production of rice crops.

The model was evaluated using data from 1986 and 1987 dry season experi-

ments on growth of rice cultivar IR64 and breeding line IR29723-143-3-2-1. It gave reasonable estimates of the weights of different plant organs (Fig. 1). However, it requires accurate values of initial weights. Simulated canopy photosynthesis agreed well with measured canopy photosynthesis.

Appropriate submodels were selected and MACROS was used to simulate potential grain yields in four situations: IR64 and IR36 in fully irrigated conditions, IR64 transplanted in rainfed lowland, and Kinandang Pula (KP) dry seeded in rainfed upland. The model was run for crops transplanted at weekly intervals for 27 yr (1960-88), and 10, 25, 75, and 90% cumulative probability yield levels for specific flowering dates computed (Fig. 2).

Yield was most strongly related to flowering date because weather

1. Simulated and observed dry matter of different plant organs. Data for IR64 obtained from IRRI Plant Physiology Department, 1986 dry season. F = observed date of flowering, M = observed date of maturity.

Grain yield (t/ha)

2. Simulated potential grain yields (rough rice, 14% moisture content) for different situations in Los Baños. The yield of weekly transplantings for 1988 are shown (•) The lines represent the yield levels that have a 10, 25, 75, and 90% probability to be exceeded (solid lines for 25 and 75%, broken lines for 10 and 90% probability).

conditions during the reproductive phase of rice development significantly affect grain yield.

Simulated potential yields can serve

as references for ongoing field trials and can facilitate interpretation of year-to-year or season-to-season differences in growth and yield. □

Grain quality

Effect of rice genotype x environment interactions on quality characters

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We tested five common rice varieties (H4, BG94-1, BG379-2, BW531, and BG34-6) at five locations in southern Sri Lanka in 1987 wet season. The locations were chosen to provide differences in annual rainfall. The cultivars were planted in a randomized

Range and analysis of variance for quality characteristics of 5 rice varieties in 5 rainfall environments. * Matara, Sri Lanka, 1987 wet season.

	Length:breadth ratio		Grain elongation (%)		Amylose (%)		Brown rice protein (%)		
Overall range		2.87-4.16		27.3-66.0		25.1-29.8		6.2-11.1	
Range of mean values		3.12-4.01		37.8-52.9		27.9-29.1		7.4- 8.8	
ANOVA									
Source	df	MS	F	MS	F	MS	F	MS	F
Varieties	4	0.5816	21.8***	156.6527	16.75***	1.3350	222.50***	1.8802	308.23***
Environments	4	0.0412	1.4 ns	196.5726	21.02***	1.3679	227.98***	2.2510	369.02***
Variety x environment	16	0.0426	1.0 ns	59.2172	6.33***	1.3228	222.13***	0.9585	157.13***
Heterogeneity	4	0.0715	2.1 ns	12.5252	0.17 ns	2.2118	2.13 ns	0.8325	0.83 ns
Residual deviations	12	0.0330	1.2 ns	74.7811	7.99***	1.0397	173.23***	1.0005	164.02***
Error	50	0.0267		9.3507		0.0060		0.0061	

* P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001, ns = not significant.

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complete block design with three replications at each location.

Both variety and environment effects were significant for grain elongation, amylose, and brown rice protein, and the variety x environment interaction was significant (see table). This means the effects were not additive. Heterogeneity between linear regressions also was not significant. But highly significant values were found for residual deviations.

Grain elongation was highest in BG34-6 and lowest in BG94-1. BW531 showed the lowest amylose content and the highest brown rice protein. BG379-2 had the highest amylose content and BG34-6 the lowest brown rice protein. Length/breadth ratio was highest in BG94-1 and lowest in BW531.

Interactions between variety and environment for the characters studied cannot be explained by linear regression. This could be due to interactions that were specific to particular combinations. The length/breadth ratio did not show significant interaction with variety and environment. □